

Navigating the Strategies to Enhance the Implementation of the Revised Biology Curriculum in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia

Frostinia Tuyenikomwene Vatileni,¹ Stanley Chombo Chombo,² & Lukas Matati Josua.³

¹*Department of Applied Educational Sciences, University of Namibia, Namibia.*

Email: frostinia@gmail.com

²*Department of Applied Educational Sciences, University of Namibia, Namibia.*

Email: schombo@unam.na

³*Department of Higher Education and Lifelong Learning, University of Namibia, Namibia. Corresponding author. Email: ljosua@unam.na*

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to investigate strategies to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia. The study employed a descriptive case study design. In this research study, the researchers decided to employ a qualitative approach because it provided a better understanding in depth of the topic at hand, by examining the teachers' experiences and roles and responsibilities in the implementation of the Biology revised curriculum. The population of this study consisted of all Biology teachers teaching in the Secondary schools of Ompundja Circuit in Namibia. A sample of ten teachers and five Heads of Departments (HODs) were purposively selected from five (5) secondary schools in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia to participate in this study. The study used the semi-structured face-to-face interview schedules as a research instrument, as they are advantageous in that they have the capacity to acquire a large amount of relevant data. The collected data were analysed qualitatively and were transcribed and coded for theme identification and analysis. Participants were able to propose different strategies to ensure effective implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit. The study suggested the provision of adequate Biology classrooms, remedial teaching of Biology or learning, provision of adequate educational infrastructures, parental involvement, as well as motivation of teachers and learners, as some of the strategies that can be used to ensure effective implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in the Ompundja Circuit, Namibia.

Keywords: Strategies, Implementation, Biology Curriculum, Namibia, Secondary Schools.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution

International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study is to investigate strategies to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia. Biology is one of the subjects in the Namibian curriculum, and it is offered in the Ompundja circuit in Namibia. The region is characterised by a high population of school-going-age children with limited teaching and learning resources, which makes it difficult to successfully implement the revised Biology curriculum. Despite this national initiative to advance education in Namibia, the previous teaching experiences of teachers for the revised Biology curriculum remain unknown and undocumented. This is particularly the case in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia, where five Secondary schools that are also implementing the revised curriculum still do not have their examination results for most subjects, including Biology, with the results for most subjects trading at a level less than 30 percent.

Teachers play a crucial role and are a defining aspect in the context of curriculum implementation; as such, it is of great importance to learn about their experiences, roles, attitudes, and views in relation to curriculum implementation (Kelly et al., 2019). Furthermore, it was also shown that learners' attitudes and behaviours are significantly impacted, as well as their academic performance, if the curriculum is not grasped properly (Kelly et al., 2019). Moreover, their research did not venture beyond a simple acknowledgement of teachers' role as crucial agents of curricular implementation. In support of this, there has been a source of concern and controversy regarding the minimal consultation with teachers by the drafters of the curriculum (Hakutumbulwa, 2021).

1.1 Research objectives

1. To identify challenges that may impede the effective implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia.
2. To propose strategies to enhance the effective implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Strategies to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology Curriculum

Developing a curriculum is a tough assignment for teachers. However, understanding what to expect and preparing ahead of time can be of great help. Various researchers (Seven & Engin, 2021; Martinez, 2021; Onuka, 2018) suggested strategies for curriculum implementation from various teaching professionals.

2.2 Teaching and learning methods

It has been found that teachers who use a specific style of evidence-based teaching and operation. Furthermore, several studies conducted on teaching and learning methods in many parts of the world have demonstrated that teaching and learning methods enhance learners' performance. Research studies conducted indicate that teaching and learning

methods used by teachers make a positive impact on learners' performance. These researchers recommended that the interactive visuals, questions, and answers are the most commonly used methods by teachers in teaching. However, Liswaniso (2019) suggests that despite the frequency of the two common methods in teaching Biology classes, various methods should be employed to increase the knowledge of teachers in teaching Biology in schools.

Put simply, the findings reveal that teacher-centered methods (writing on the board and lecturing) do not enhance learners' performance compared to when teachers apply learner-centred methods such as group work, questions and answers, discussions, and sharing of ideas, and learners reading in silence. Similarly, in their study that looked at teachers' perception on the causes of poor performance of grade 12 learners in Namibia's selected Secondary schools, Maemeko et al. (2017) express that some reasons that may have caused the poor performance could be poor teaching and learning methods some teachers used when they are teaching, especially Biology and science subjects.

2.3 Teaching and learning resources

In Namibia, inadequate instructional resources such as textbooks hinder effective revised curriculum implementation and may lead to poor academic performance among learners in Ompundja Circuit (Josua, 2022). Implementation Research studies conducted in Turkey by Seven and Engin (2021) reveal that the usage of Biology teaching and learning resources is very important to the success of Biology teaching and learning. Seven and Engin (2021) mention that Biology teachers who mainly depend on schoolbooks as the only source of knowledge and leave other learning resources holds back makes learners perform poorly in Biology. Furthermore, skilled Biology teachers always review the importance and value of their textbooks, and they can change them if they do not fulfil the needs of learners (Seven & Engin, 2021).

In the same vein, Howard and Major (2018) support the view that using teaching and learning resources that are amusing and enjoyable makes the subject clear and comprehensible for learners. They further argue that using supportive teaching resources to teach Biology motivates the learners to learn better and to be more aware of the learning activities, and increases the success in exams. Moreover, teaching materials have to be used at all levels so that the knowledge of Biology becomes higher in teaching and learning (Seven & Engin, 2021). According to the study findings done by a South African scholar (Carey, 2014), rural schools need support from the government, especially financially, to enhance conducive teaching and learning environments that help to improve learners' performance. The availability of teaching resources in schools for Biology lessons is essential for the success of the subject. Learners must have textbooks available to them in order to engage in self-activities and self-learning (Carey, 2014). The findings also align with the findings of, who cited that the learners do not have luxury resources to enhance their learning at home and are therefore unable to improve their knowledge except when they are at school. This may lead to them losing interest in their schoolwork and then performing poorly (Carey, 2014).

Orodho and Benjamin (2021) believe that learners perform poorly because the teaching resources are not available to support them. Similarly, Howard and Major (2018) emphasize teacher-designed materials. Howard and Major (2018) further stated that a teacher can develop materials that incorporate elements of the learners' knowledge, or at least provide opportunities for acknowledgement and use alongside Biology. In addition, teachers' prepared materials and activities are exactly at the right level for particular learners, to ensure appropriate challenge and level of success (Howard & Major, 2018). Chirimhana et al. (2020) contended that the provision of enough instructional media/materials will assist a lot in improving the performance of learners in Biology in Namibian schools. Similarly, Zeripi (2017) points out that teachers may have the required skills in teaching, but teaching effectively can be a challenge if the necessary teaching and learning resources are not in place.

Admittedly, Junias (2019) stated that learners' difficulties in Biology could be attributed to a lack of Biology teaching and learning resources in schools. The above arguments seem to indicate that if Biology teachers do not have the necessary teaching and learning resources, it would be difficult for them to teach effectively, and the performance of learners in Biology is adversely affected.

2.4 Parental involvement

Studies by Knapp (2016) in Australia, Martinez (2021) in the USA, and Kalayci and Oz (2018) in Turkey acknowledge that parental involvement is the key to successful learners' academic performance. According to Kalayci and Oz (2018), parents or other caregivers are the first teachers of children, and this role continues even when they start school. In addition, parents need to become collaborative partners with teachers in order to provide an environment that assists their children's performance at school. However, findings of their studies reveal that some parents argue that their involvement does not create a significant difference in their children's biological development.

According to Lara and Saracostti (2019), the majority of the parents are uneducated and unfamiliar with the syllabus of Biology as a science subject. It is therefore difficult for them to participate in a way that is required by the teachers. However, being involved in their children's learning is considered crucial and influential in the learners' performance. Parental involvement plays a vital role in a learner's academic performance (Channon et al., 2020). Irrespective of ethnicity, research has shown that parental monitoring leads to higher academic achievement due to the fact that parental attention helps learners remain focused at school (Lara & Saracostti, 2019).

Based on the results of his studies, Badugela (2019) found that parental involvement is positively related to expectations of learners having a highly positive attitude towards education, thus making learners more likely to excel. Approximately 90% of learners are unable to get assistance from their parents in Biology (Lara & Saracostti, 2019). They defined parental involvement as limited, and because most of the parents are uneducated, cannot read and write, and they do not even understand their

role in their children's education. Martinez (2021) further argues that the lack of parents' participation in schools hinders performance.

On the same note, Knapp (2016) argues that Biology teachers cannot do their work effectively without the support of parents. Knapp (2016) further notes that parents need to know what is happening in Biology classrooms in order to support the schools, because increased parental involvement will help remedy the problem of poor academic performance in schools.

Ebuta et al. (2014) conducted a research study in Nigeria which explored the influence of parental involvement on their children's education and their academic achievement in Biology. The result of the study revealed a significant positive relationship between parental involvement in their children's education and learners' academic achievement in Biology. Based on that, it was concluded that for learners' academic achievement in Biology to be effectively enhanced, parents should be interested and work with their children in their education. This will complement the teachers' effort to improve learners' academic achievement in Biology (Ebuta et al., 2014).

On the contrary, Sibomana et al. (2021) argue that, in Rwanda, parental involvement may not lead to the attainment of improved performance in Biology because it has been noted that the classroom is almost the only setting where learners are exposed to Biology, and teachers are almost the only model and source of input for learners. However, a study that was conducted in Nigeria (2014) maintains that parents need to become more involved in helping their children to improve their schoolwork, providing encouragement, arranging for appropriate study time and space, modelling desired behaviour such as reading for pleasure, monitoring homework, and actively tutoring their children at home. According to Nkandi (2015) in Namibia, no clear documentation exists of how parental involvement can be promoted in rural schools and among parents living in high-risk communities. Research results of his study point out that parental involvement is difficult to carry out in Namibia's rural schools and among parents from poor communities. In his study, Badugela (2019) posits that parents' involvement in the children's education is multi-dimensional; it can range from parents directly helping their children with Biology homework to parents establishing high expectations for their children's Biology learning in schools.

Nkandi (2015) furthermore notes that the quality of parental involvement in the education of their children is an important factor when determining the children's performance in Biology. This is consistent with the observation by Lara and Saracosti (2019) that parental involvement is rooted in the belief that, in order for schools to educate all children effectively, parents and families should become fully involved in the process.

2.5 Teacher and learner motivation

Channon et al. (2020) regarded motivation as an important factor in learning science subjects. According to Othman and Shaqair (2020), motivation is one of the primary forces influencing the teaching and learning of Biology as a science subject. Othman and Shaqair (2020) claim that motivation has been broadly recognised as a major aspect that determines the success and level of science learning. They regard motivation as one of the primary components that contribute to participation in Biology, as it influences the level of dynamic and personal engagement in the entire teaching and learning process of Biology.

In a study that explored the impact of motivation in Biology as a science subject in Iran, Alizadeh (2016) asserts that teachers can play a significant role in motivating learners to learn Biology, for them to perform well. Alizadeh (2016) highlights that learners become motivated to learn when they see themselves as capable individuals and use educational materials suited to their level. Learners are further motivated when they live in a safe environment and can express their psychological needs for achievement and recognition. If learners are well motivated, they recognise that learning benefits them directly and have the freedom to make choices, take responsibilities for their learning, and experience more successes than failures.

Likewise, Abramo et al. (2019, p.67) express that motivated learners are enthusiastic, eager to work hard, concentrate on the tasks given, do not require constant encouragement, are willing to confront challenges, and could even motivate others through collaborative learning. In their research study, Sibomana et al. (2021) establish that there is no doubt that motivation plays an important role in learners' good performance in subjects. Kayombo (2017) goes as far as suggesting that, without motivation, even gifted individuals may not be successful in the long run, no matter how good the curricula and the teachers are.

Chirimbana and Haimbangu (2018) argue that poor performance by Biology learners is often caused by Biology teachers' lack of motivation. A study that was carried out in Namibia, Nkandi (2015), suggests that motivation determines attitudes towards learning, while, on the other hand, the attitudes that one has towards the target subject influence the extent to which they are motivated to teach and learn Biology.

Nkandi (2015) further implies that good learners' performance in Biology examinations cannot be considered without motivated to learning. Similarly, Simasiku (2017) posits that teachers' motivation towards Biology creates positive attitudes and enthusiasm in learners towards Biology. Subsequently, motivation makes learners perform better in Biology, as it opens their minds and expands their knowledge to explore new ideas and achieve their success.

Along the same line, Simasiku (2017) indicates that if a school is to improve learners' and teachers' performance in Biology examinations, then attention should be given to their level of motivation and the support they receive. He further notes that motivated learners are higher achievers than unmotivated ones. In light of the above

arguments, it could be argued that poor motivation of Biology teachers and learners leads to poor commitment and, as a result, learners end up performing poorly in Biology. Therefore, Biology teachers might need to develop means and methods that motivate learners to learn Biology.

2.6 Administrative and management support

According to a research study conducted by Carl (2019), administrative and management support is one of the most important components in an education system for teachers to succeed and develop new ideas for the new curriculum implementation. School administrators are responsible for both teaching the teachers and learners to work better and succeed (Chirimbana & Haimbangu, 2018). In Namibia, Josua's (2022) study revealed that teachers and principals are managing and leading as schools in the Ompundja Circuit, and they are faced with challenges when implementing the revised curriculum for basic education. The challenges range from inadequate resources, insufficient training, heavy workloads, and a lack of stakeholder support.

Chirimbana and Haimbangu (2018) further stated that one of the duties of the school administrator and manager is to monitor the learners' success and to make teachers understand what they can do to improve their learners' performance. They further stated that school administrators communicate with parents about their children's performance because at many times, parents may not know how their children are progressing at school.

Recent research has demonstrated that whether or not teachers feel supported in implementing the new curriculum, the implementation of a new curriculum still depends on administrative support and management support (Carl, 2019).

2.7 Teacher support

Channon et al. (2020) found that when a new program needs to be implemented, educators require guidance and support to implement such a new program. Teachers cannot implement a curriculum effectively if they are not given support on how to implement such a curriculum. Channon et al. (2020) suggest that training and professional development that includes both introductory and advanced training on the curriculum must be introduced to teachers. They further stated that teachers implement any curriculum effectively when they are given training on how to implement such a curriculum.

On the other hand, Anderson and Elloumi (2017) suggest that ongoing feedback to teachers about their use of the curriculum supports learners through practice-based coaching. Onuka (2018) discovered the necessity of teachers' support in carrying out curricula objectives that are more effectively to the implementation of a curriculum. He further stated that teachers are more able to create learning tasks that are in line with curriculum goals while also being developmentally appropriate, if they are given support. Uka (2018) suggests that teachers are the implementers of the curriculum; they should be given support in all circumstances to implement such a curriculum effectively.

Teachers' support is important because it enables teachers to use teaching strategies and get teaching resources that are appropriate to the curriculum being implemented (Davis, 2018).

Davis (2018) asserts that effective support gives teachers opportunities to apply new knowledge and skills in their everyday work, for them to be able to deliver quality teaching to the learners, which also results in effective curriculum implementation. Davis (2018), furthermore, stated that if teachers are supported, they are more likely to create teaching and learning materials that are in line with the curriculum objectives. Alderman (2016) added that if teachers are asked to implement a new curriculum, they should be provided with ongoing In-Service Training to deal with the problems and difficulties encountered during the implementation process. Similarly, Chirimbana and Haimbangu (2018) found that the purpose of teachers' training, especially in science subjects such as Biology, necessitates a focus on teaching learners how to best interpret the curriculum so that their needs are aligned with appropriate instructional practices. Effective curriculum delivery is a principal indicator of quality basic education, and teachers are the vehicles through which the curriculum is to be delivered; support should be rendered to teachers (Chirimbana & Haimbangu, 2018).

2.8 Teacher learner relationships

Building a positive relationship with your learners is an excellent way to combat chronic absenteeism, and learners are more motivated to attend classes when they know their teachers care for them and help them to succeed in their lives (Alderman, 2016). According to Channon et al. (2020), positive personal relationships with the learners can also raise their intrinsic motivation to learn, and when learners feel interested in their own work, they develop a love of learning that benefits them for their entire lives. Channon et al. (2020) further stated that positive teacher-learner relationships help learners to learn how to evaluate and manage their behaviour, which in turn helps them to reach their academic goals, and over time, this can strengthen their academic achievements. In the same line, Chirimbana and Haimbangu (2018) posit that teachers and parents should understand that a problematic bond is one of the factors that can contribute to poor learners' academic performance and educational growth.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

To gain an in-depth understanding of strategies to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia. The study employed a descriptive case study design. According to Albert (2021), descriptive case studies are those that have a specific occurrence and are examined in great depth, making participants frame their initial hypotheses and research objectives in clear, specific language.

In this research study, the researchers decided to employ a qualitative approach because it provided a better understanding in depth of the topic at hand, by examining the teachers' experiences and roles and responsibilities in the implementation of the Biology revised curriculum. Furthermore, a qualitative approach was therefore an appropriate approach for this study as it enabled the researcher to determine the teachers' experiences and roles and responsibilities in the implementation of the Biology revised curriculum.

3.2 Population of the study

According to Johnson and Christensen (2020), population refers to the large group to which a researcher wants to generalize the sample results from the total group that the researcher is interested in learning more about. The population of this study consisted of all Biology teachers teaching in the Secondary schools of Ompundja Circuit in Namibia.

3.3 Sample and sampling technique

A sample refers to the number of individuals, items, or events selected from a population in such a way that they are characteristically representative of that population (Somekh & Lewin, 2018). This research study made use of a purposive sampling technique to select the participants. A sample of ten teachers and five Heads of Departments (HODs) were purposively selected from five (5) Secondary schools in Ompundja Circuit in Namibia to participate in this study. The selection of schools was based on their distances from the researcher's place. Teachers, on the other hand, were selected based on their availability, experience, subject taught, and positions they held at their schools. Thus, this sampling technique was essential since the participants possessed appropriate levels of understanding and knowledge about the subject being studied, as they had lived experiences.

3.4 Research instruments

The study used the semi-structured face-to-face interview schedules as a research instrument, as they are advantageous in that they have the capacity to acquire a large amount of relevant data. The researchers used a voice recorder and a notebook to record and jot down participants' responses. The oral interviews were recorded with the voice recorder in order to capture all the rich information from the purposefully selected participants.

3.5 Data analysis

The collected data were analysed qualitatively and were transcribed and coded for theme identification and analysis. Data analysis is an essential part of the research study. Baker (2019) states that data analysis is all about making a series of deliberate, critical choices about the meanings and values of the data gathered and making justified decisions in terms of research. The study used the thematic analysis model to determine the themes

and sub-themes to analyse patterns, similarities, and differences discovered in the study. The thematic analysis model allowed flexibility in interpreting the data and examining the perspectives of different research participants.

3.6 Ethical issues

An ethical clearance certificate reference number: KMC1011 was issued by the University of Namibia's Research Ethics Committee in accordance with the University's Research Ethics Policy and Guidelines. Furthermore, permission was granted by the Oshana Regional Council's Directorate of Education, Arts and Culture. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants by signing the Consent Form. All participants were informed of the right to leave the interview at any time they felt like without being coerced. Anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were ensured through data storage in a password-protected Google Cloud and the use of pseudonyms.

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Challenges and possible Strategies to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology curriculum

Under this section, participants were asked to identify possible challenges and propose how to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology curriculum. These have been highlighted under the following themes:

Theme 1: Design educational policies

During the interviews, participants in the study indicated that the current policies do not seem to effectively improve the provision of resources in schools, especially in schools that are in deep remote areas of the Ompundja circuit.

Teacher 1 in the study had the following to say:

The current policies don't seem to support and improve the provision of resources like library facilities and computer facilities in rural schools at all". These sentiments were supported by HOD 1, who also said that, "If only the government would be able to provide and monitor the provision of resources like textbooks, our learners do not have textbooks at all, especially for this new curriculum, as the old textbooks are no longer useful, they are phased out. Imagine teaching Biology without a single textbook for the learners! We are not really having policies that seem to support this.

Theme 2: Provision of adequate Biology classrooms

After conducting interviews with participants, it shows that it is of utmost importance to provide adequate Biology classrooms for teaching and learning. With reference to the results of the study, participants responded to the provision of adequate Biology classrooms as follows:

Teacher 2 responded as follows:

If each school is provided with its own Biology laboratory and adequate equipment, the teaching and learning process will be highly improved and ultimately improve learners' performance in Biology." This was echoed by HOD 2, who also said that, "We need to have a Biology laboratory which is well furnished so that learners can be taught in conducive environments.

Teacher 3 also added and said that:

The provision of Biology classroom laboratory will make Biology teaching and learning exciting, and this will also improve the learners' perceptions and attitudes toward Biology.

Theme 3: Remedial Biology classes

With regard to remedial Biology classes, participants were positive and in support of remedial classes to enhance learning in Biology. The above statement is supported by the views of different participants as follows:

The view of teacher 4:

I think remedial classes for Biology lessons during study time would help our learners ". These citations were echoed by Teacher 8, who also said that, "Schools need more library facilities, so that they come up with more practical sessions every two weeks, and this will also help learners to learn Biology. On this issue, this is what HOD 3 had to say: "Educational funds for educational travelling tours that help and expose learners to different environments may help them to improve their Biology skills.

Another participant also supported the idea by saying that:

In the world of the digital age, it's paramount to have access to computers, for educational games, quizzes,

and biological games, and the use of biology around the globe, that's what our rural learners need to improve their skills, in Biology (Teacher 6).

These results reveal that Biology remedial classes need to be introduced in order for the revised Biology curriculum to be implemented effectively.

Theme 4: Formulation and implementation of policies

With regards to the formulation and implementation of policies, participants were positive and in support of the formulation and implementation of policies that can improve learners' Biology results. Here are the responses from the participants:

None of our teachers were trained to teach the revised curriculum; new policies need to be formulated to allow teachers to be trained on how to implement the revised curriculum, as this has already been a problem for our learners' performance in Biology," (HOD 2). These citations were supported by Teacher 7, who indicated that, "The new curriculum content is really a lot compared to the old one, and the time allocated to finish the content is inadequate. It also requires different pedagogical approaches in teaching Biology, thus new policies should be formulated to allow teachers to implement this revised curriculum easily.

On the same issue, this is what HOD 3 had to say:

In comparison with the previous notes from the old curriculum, there is an increase in the basic competences. The government needs to formulate a policy that makes it easier for the teachers to implement this revised curriculum.

As summarised from participants' conversations, it can be deduced that the formulation and implementation of policies will help in improving academic results for the learners in Biology.

Theme 5: Provision of adequate educational infrastructure

The results on the provision of adequate educational infrastructures indicated that the available classes have not supported learning effectively since the number of learners keeps increasing each year. Here are the responses from participants:

Teacher 4:

Every year we have a large number of learners in each class, and this year we are short of chairs and tables. The schools need to come up with fundraising events for it to buy necessary teaching infrastructures”. This was supported by HOD 4 who said that, “During winter the absenteeism rate increases, because some learners travel long distances in the cold weather to schools, because they do not have a hostel”. On this issue, this is what HOD 2 had to say, “Sometimes the teacher will not finish marking a class activity within the lesson because learners are so many in a class and some make noise especially at the back.

These findings show that substandard educational infrastructures continue to be a barrier to quality education and learners’ performance in Biology and other Science subjects. The provision of adequate educational infrastructures will thus enhance high performance among Biology learners. The findings indicate that buildings are crucial elements of a conducive learning environment in schools.

Theme 6: Policies that engage the involvement of parents

As reflected from interviews, the research participants indicated that parents are not involved in the education system, and there are no policies making provision for involving parents in education. These were the participants’ responses for recommendations to involve parents in their children’s education:

Teacher 7 said:

Some parents do not show up during parents’ meetings; they do not even know how their children are doing at school, they do not even support their children in learning.” The above sentiment was supported by Teacher 2 when he said, “Some parents do not understand the importance of education, yet that is why sometimes they keep their children at home, missing the lessons, especially during the farming season, and this contributes to poor performance.

The same thoughts were supported by HOD 2, who said that, “There should be some educational programmes to include our dear parents in their children’s school life.” Teacher 8 also shared her views on this issue by saying that, “There must be educational rules that involve parents in education. Furthermore, scheduling social evenings and invitations to social events like end-of-year celebrations can be used to force parents to take part in the education of their children.”

These findings from the participants indicate that the issue of parental involvement plays a major role in influencing the children's education.

Theme 7: Motivation of teachers and learners

The participants showed that teachers and learners are demotivated due to the lack of proper infrastructures, such as roads, and the lack of facilities, such as Biology study rooms. In short, here are the participants' responses:

It's possible around here to advertise the teaching post, but even before the end of the term, the qualified young teachers feel discouraged and get a transfer. This leaves our learners being taught by three different Biology teachers in a year," (Teacher 3). The same views and thoughts were shared by Teacher 1, who said that "If the educational infrastructures are improved and provision is made, I believe it will motivate our teachers and even learners will be eager to explore the new ideas, for example, utilizing the Biology study rooms to solve biological problems together, and learners' interest will be fostered.

The same opinions were alluded to by Teacher 9, who also said that, "If the government can increase the salary of Biology teachers in some remote areas, it will motivate and attract the effective, qualified teachers," (Teacher 9).

Based on the results, it is the researcher's opinion that learners and teachers should be motivated to enhance the teaching and learning of Biology. This can be an effective mechanism for a smooth implementation of a revised Biology curriculum.

5. DISCUSSION

Several strategies to enhance the implementation of the revised Biology curriculum have been highlighted in this study and discussed, from designing educational policies, provision of adequate Biology classrooms, remedial Biology classes, formulation and implementation of policies, provision of adequate educational infrastructures, policies that engage the involvement of parents, and motivation of teachers and learners.

The design of educational policies was found not to be an effective strategy to enhance the revised Biology curriculum implementation. Teachers, furthermore, indicated that the current policies do not seem to effectively improve the provision of resources in schools, especially in deep remote areas of Ompundja Circuit. The findings contradict Dzimiri and Marimo (2015), who stated that designing public policies that effectively improve the provision of resources in schools will help to mitigate the lack and inadequate availability of resources such as textbooks and other teaching aids, such as posters and charts.

There is no way that the goal and objectives of education can be achieved without putting in place some mechanisms in the school system. Part of the integral pre-requisites to be put in place toward the actualisation of the educational goal and objectives requires adequate provision of resources, maximum utilization, and appropriate management of educational resources to avoid wastage and to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process (Dzimiri & Marimo, 2015).

Participants in the study recognised the need for the provision of adequate Biology classrooms as a need or strategy to enhance the revised Biology curriculum implementation. They, furthermore, stated that they need to have Biology laboratories that are well furnished so that learners can be taught in conducive environments. These findings support the findings of Onuka (2018), who states that the Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture should outsource funds and partner with non-government organisations in order to build sufficient classrooms that can accommodate all the learners in the schools. Subject specialists and advisors who are currently in district offices should be used as tutors, and they should be stationed at the various set venues. This will cut the costs of purchasing science materials for individual schools and will also minimize the costs of building individual science laboratories in schools.

The present study established that remedial classes enhance the teaching of biology in the Ompundja Circuit. This clearly shows that teachers in the Ompundja Circuit conduct remedial classes for Biology. This finding is similar to Brodier (2019), who asserted that through teachers' training, teachers gain more knowledge and experiences, and are likely to conduct remedial Biology classes, which will assist learners to improve their Biology content, and at the same time, it motivates learners to learn and explore Biology further.

This study found that the formulation and implementation of policies help to enhance the revised Biology curriculum implementation. The findings support the earlier findings of Emery (2020), who revealed that any curriculum changes should also involve changes in teaching and learning methods in order to cope with newly introduced or transformed content.

The study discovered that many teachers had little mastery of the subject matter required by changes in the school curriculum, particularly for those who started to implement the changes for the first time. The results on the provision of adequate educational infrastructures indicated that the available classes have not supported learning effectively since the number of learners keeps increasing each year. The findings, furthermore, showed that substandard educational infrastructures continue to be a barrier to quality education and learners' performance in Biology and other science subjects. The provision of inadequate infrastructures is a challenge, and findings also indicate that buildings are crucial elements of a learning environment in schools. This supports Abramo et al. (2019, p.67) findings, who suggested that "the government must also provide physical facilities such as classrooms, laboratories, workshops, and libraries to create a conducive environment for the curriculum implementation to take place".

Workshops such as instructional materials and resources workshops, on curriculum implementation, have a great influence on the implementation of the Biology curriculum (Abramo et al., 2019). During the instructional materials and resources workshop, curriculum implementers select and use instructional materials and resources like textbooks, digital resources, audiovisual resources, and other teaching aids that support the curriculum.

The results on policies that engage the involvement of parents indicated that there are no policies that force parents to participate in the education of their children. The findings contradict Kalayci and Oz (2018), who stated that parents or other caregivers are the first teachers of children, and this role continues even when they start school. In addition, parents need to become collaborative partners with teachers in order to provide an environment that assists their children's performance at school.

However, findings of their studies reveal that some parents argue that their involvement in education does not create a significant difference in their children's learning and development. On motivation of teachers and learners, participants in the research study recognise the need for motivation of teachers and learners as a strategy to enhance the revised Biology curriculum implementation, such as infrastructure. Participants, furthermore, indicated that the lack of proper infrastructures, such as roads, is already a discouragement, as many young teachers are coming and going due to the lack of facilities such as Biology study rooms, libraries, computer laboratories, overcrowded classes, lack of textbooks, and lack of internet connection.

The findings of the present study align with Othman and Shaqair (2020), who stated that motivation is one of the primary forces influencing the teaching and learning of Biology as a science subject. They further claimed that motivation has been broadly recognised as a major aspect that determines the success and level of science learning. They regard motivation as one of the primary components that contribute to Biology as a science subject. Motivation influences the level of dynamic and personal engagement in the entire teaching and learning process for Biology.

In the same vein is Alizadeh (2016) underscores that learners become motivated to learn when they perceive themselves as competent individuals. Learners are also motivated when they work with materials tailored to their level and can see clear goals in their activities. Additionally, their studies become more meaningful when they are presented with challenging tasks. Furthermore, learners' motivation is fostered when they live in a safe environment and have the opportunity to express their psychological needs for success, recognition, and acceptance. Their intrinsic motivation is enhanced when they understand that learning is for their own benefit rather than solely for their teachers.

6. CONCLUSION

Participants were able to propose different strategies to ensure effective implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in Ompundja Circuit. The study suggested the provision of adequate Biology classrooms, remedial teaching of Biology or learning, provision of adequate educational infrastructures, parental involvement, as well as motivation of teachers and learners, as some of the strategies that can be used to ensure effective implementation of the revised Biology curriculum in the Ompundja Circuit in Namibia. Furthermore, the study concluded that the current policies do not seem to effectively address the provision of resources and educational facilities, especially in schools located in remote areas. Thus, these policies need to be amended to make sure that all schools receive resources and educational facilities regardless of where they are found. The study also concluded that the negative attitudes or perceptions towards Biology can be mitigated by motivating teachers and learners by meeting their educational needs, such as providing schools with Biology equipment, textbooks, and a safe learning environment that is conducive and learner-centered.

REFERENCES

- Abramo, G., Cicero, T., & D'Angelo, C. A. (2019). What is the appropriate length of the publication period over which to assess research performance? *Scientometrics*, 93(3), 1005–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-012-0714-9>
- Albert, B. (2021). Comparative Analysis of Public and Private Educational Institutions : A Case Study of District Vehari, Pakistan. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(16), 122–131.
- Alderman, J. (2016). Use of teaching aids in language teaching. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 4(3), 247–250. <http://ijrar.com/>
- Alizadeh, M. (2016). The Impact of Motivation on English Language Learning in the Gulf States. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 2(4), 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v2n4p123>
- Anderson, T., & Elloumi, F. (2017). *Teaching in an online learning context*. Athabasca University Press.
- Badugela, T. M. (2019). *Problems facing educators in implementing the national curriculum statement: the case of Tshifhena Secondary School, Vhembe district, Limpopo Province, South Africa*. Unpublished Thesis. University of South Africa.
- Baker, T. (2019). *Doing Social Research* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Brodier, K. (2019). Effective Classroom-Management & Positive Teaching. *English Language Teaching*, 9(1), 163. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n1p163>
- Carey, K. (2014). Situational determinants of heavy drinking among college students. *Counsel. Psychol.*, 4(2), 23–29.
- Carl, A. (2019). *Teacher Empowerment through Curriculum Development Theory and Practice*. Juta & Company.
- Channon, J., Smith, M., Head, H., Macrae, M., & Chasakara, A. (2020). *New General Mathematics Book 3 and 4: Ordinary Level Course* (3rd ed.). Print Originators.
- Chirimbana, H., & Haimbangu, G. (2018). A comparative study of the performances of students in Mathematics at two selected schools in Oshana Region. *NIED Journal for Educational Curriculum*, 2(3), 89–99.
- Chirimbana, M., Miranda, H., & Nakashole, S. (2020). *Mathematics in Namibia: A comparative review of the Namibian Educational Curriculum*. Mathematics Congress.
- Davis, E. (2018). *Teachers' experiences in the implementation of the Technology Education curriculum in one secondary school in the St. George East District in Trinidad* [University of the West Indies].

- Dzimiri, W., & Marimo, S. (2015). Challenges faced in the implementation of the Zimbabwe localised Advanced level Geography syllabus: A case of Gweru district high schools. *Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 4(2), 52–56.
- Ebuta, Catherine & Ekpo, O. E.-E. (2014). Influence of Parental Involvement on their Children's Education and their Academic achievement in the English language. *Global Journal of Engineering Research*, 13(1), 41.
- Emery, H. (2020). A global study of primary English teachers' qualifications, training, and career development. In *British Council ELT Research Papers Volume 1*. http://englishagenda.britishcouncil.org/sites/ec/files/British_Council_WEB_pdf_o.pdf
- Hakutumbulwa, G. (2021). *Teachers' experiences regarding implementation of the revised Social Studies: The case of Khomas Region, Namibia*. University of Namibia.
- Howard, J., & Major, J. (2018). *Guidelines for Designing Effective English Language Teaching Materials: Why English Language Teachers May Choose to Design their own Materials*. January 2004, 101–109.
- Johnson, B. R., & Christensen, L. (2020). *Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Approaches* (7th ed.). Sage Publication.
- Josua, L. M. (2022). *Challenges facing school teachers and principals in managing and implementing the revised curriculum in Ompundja circuit in Namibia* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Namibia). https://repository.unam.edu.na/server/api/core/bitstreams/985a0304-8db5-40c2-9245-8c4c0f74a9ae/content?utm_source=copilot.com
- Junias, R. (2019). *Factors affecting the teaching of English reading skills in a second language of grade 3 learners*. Unpublished Thesis. University of South Africa.
- Kalayci, M., & Oz, I. (2018). Parental Involvement: The Missing Link in School Achievement. Preventing School Failure: *Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 55(3), 115–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10459880903472876>
- Kayombo, C. (2017). *The role of parents' involvement in students*. Unpublished Thesis. University of Tanzania.
- Kelly, N., Wright, N., Dawes, L., Kerr, J., & Robertson, A. (2019). Co-design for curriculum planning: A model for professional development for high school teachers. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 44(7), 84–107. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2019v44n7.6>
- Knapp, R. (2016). *The parent perspective of parental involvement, academic achievement, and Latino fathers in an urban school*. Unpublished Thesis. Prairie View A&M University.

- Lara, L., & Saracostti, M. (2019). Effect of parental involvement on children's academic achievement in Chile. *Frontiers in Psychology, 10*(JUN), 1–5.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01464>
- Liswaniso, J. (2019). *An Investigation Into the Teaching of Biology and Physical* (Issue April). University of Namibia.
- Maemeko, E. L., Nkengbeza, D., & Ntabi, M. L. (2017). Teachers' perceptions on the causes of poor academic performance of grade 12 learners in four selected schools in the Zambezi Region of Namibia. *IJRDO - Journal of Educational Research* (ISSN: 2456-2947), 2(4), 93–110.
<http://www.ijrdo.org/index.php/er/article/view/184>
- Martinez, A. (2021). *Parent involvement and its effects on student academic achievement. Unpublished Thesis*. California State University, Stanislaus.
- Nkandi, S. (2015). Factors influencing grade 12 learners' performance in English as a second language in two selected senior secondary schools in the Omusati education region, Unpublished Thesis. [University of Namibia]. In *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*.
- Onuka, O. (2018). Impact of In-Service Training and Staff Development on Workers' Job Performance and Optimal Productivity in Public Secondary Schools in Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice, 7*(33), 183–189.
- Orodho, J. A., & Benjamin, B. (2021). Teaching and Learning Resource Availability and Teachers' Effective Classroom Management and Content Delivery in Secondary Schools in Huye District, Rwanda. *Journal of Education and Practice, 5*(9), 111–122.
- Othman, H. G., & Shaqair, I. H. (2020). A study on Kurdish students' attitudes to group work in the EFL classroom. *European Scientific Journal, 11*(11), 290–303.
- Seven, A., & Engin, E. (2021). The Perceptions of Students Learning Turkish as a Foreign Language Towards "Writing in Turkish." *World Journal of Education, 11*(4), 9. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v11n4p9>
- Sibomana, A., Karegeya, C., & Sentongo, J. (2021). Factors Affecting Secondary School Students' Academic Achievements in Chemistry. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research, 20*(12), 114–126.
<https://doi.org/10.26803/IJLTER.20.12.7>
- Simasiku, E. (2017). *Communicative Language Teaching: Learning Language through Meaningful Interaction* (M. Ferreira (Ed.)). Macmillan.
- Somekh, B., & Lewin, C. (2018). *Theory and Methods in Social Research* (B. Somekh & C. Lewin (Eds.); 2nd ed.). Sage Publication.

- Uka, O. (2018). Perspectives on curriculum design: comparing the spiral and the network models. *Research Matters*, 30(8), 8–11.
<http://www.cambridgeassessment.org.uk/research-matters/>
- Zeripi, H. E. (2017). *Investigating teaching methods used by primary school teachers in Otjiherero at a combined school in Okahandja circuit, Namibia*. Unpublished Thesis. University of Namibia.